

Towards Powering Gemini South with Zero CO₂ Emission

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In view of the urgency of countering the increasing effects of climate change, NOIRLab has decided to lead by example with an ambitious environmental sustainability program. Our target is a 30% reduction in the organization's carbon footprint from travel and electricity usage by late 2027, based on approved 5-year funding. Additional funding may allow us to reach a 50% reduction.

Figure 1: An aerial view of Gemini South in the Andes of Northern Chile. The solar photovoltaic panels were installed in 2016 and already provide roughly 20% of the power needed to run the telescope.
Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA

Meeting this goal will eliminate 2500 tons of CO₂ equivalent emissions every year, or roughly the same as the emissions from 500 typical US households. The program is outlined [on our website](#). The NOIRLab sustainability program consists of three parts: reduction of travel paid for by NOIRLab funds, installation of energy-efficient equipment, and production of renewable energy at our sites. In addition to the current projects that will get us to the 30% reduction in our carbon footprint, we have received funding from the National Science Foundation for the first phase of an ambitious project to supply all of Gemini South's mountain facility electricity needs through renewable energy.

During 2016, we installed a 207 kW solar panel array at Gemini South (Figure 1). This system produces about 20% of the electricity needed at the

Gemini South telescope, or the same amount of electricity as it would take to power about 35 US residential households. This system will have paid for itself in 2023.

With the new funding from NSF, we have started the first phase of a project to install additional solar panels and, eventually, battery storage. The funding will provide solar panels with a total collection capacity of about 800 kW, four times as large as the current system. The planned location of this 800 kW system is shown in Figure 2. The new solar panel array will be located below the ridge where Gemini South and the current solar array are located. This location has sufficient space for this large system, as well as for future extensions to power Rubin Observatory, if funding for this can be secured. The system will be about 500m from the closest electrical transmission lines, so new transmission lines will be necessary

as shown on the figure. The array itself will measure about 50m by 130m and consist of 2000 individual panels.

Completing the planned system of the solar panel array and battery storage system requires detailed engineering design, including a survey of the proposed site for suitability and for endangered species and historical artifacts. Additional funding will be requested to allow installation of roughly 3 MWh of battery storage, a system capable of powering ~100 typical US households for 24 hours. The system will power Gemini South for one night. The battery storage will be recharged the next day, while the solar panel array will provide the daytime electricity needs of the telescope.

We are aiming for completion of the full system, comprising the solar panels and battery storage, by the second half of 2024 if funding allows.

Figure 2: The planned solar panel array will consist of 2000 individual solar panels and is expected to measure 50m by 130m. The current Gemini South 207 kW solar panel array can be seen on the roof of the support building to the left of the dome and on the ground to the right of the dome. Based on a satellite image from Google Earth. Credit: GoogleEarth/NOIRLab